

Mapping crises, communities and capitalism on OpenStreetMap: situating humanitarian mapping in the (open source) mapping supply chain

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Founded in the aftermath of the 2010 earthquake in Haiti, the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team (HOT) helps both globally remote and local in-person volunteers to identify roads, buildings, and other features on the OpenStreetMap (OSM) platform. Created as a “free, editable map of the world,” OSM has enabled the mass-creation of volunteered geographical information (VGI) on a scale that is now more accurate than proprietary maps in many places, particularly as “crisis-mapping” has emerged as a means to gather real-time data on areas that have been affected by natural disasters or socio-political conflicts. OSM has also become a site of resistance, where local and indigenous communities have engaged in mapping projects to reclaim autonomy, agency, and space through the historically contested practice of (digital) mapping. For these reasons, such crowdsourced maps have increasingly been used by humanitarian organisations to facilitate aid and disaster relief, and as open training data for algorithms learning how to automatically detect features through Artificial Intelligence (AI). As a key partner of humanitarian, corporate, and local actors, and having mobilised over 200,000 volunteers since 2010, HOT lies at the crux of these ongoing entanglements and contestations, both within and around the field of OSM.

Previous studies of crowdsourced geographical information and crisis-mapping have generally revolved around quantitative analyses of OSM’s data, focusing on the credibility of the data itself, the makeup of the communities that contribute to it, the effects of “event-centric” crowdsourcing, or “newcomer retention” in humanitarian mapping [1]. Alternatively, they have also focused on the “spatial knowledge”, “hacker political imaginary”, and gender composition of mappers themselves [2].

Parallel studies of other volunteer-driven communities like “Wikipedians” have taken similar approaches, analysing “user-generated content” and the motivations behind them [3]. Both hacking [4] and free and open source software (F/OSS) [5] have also been explored ethnographically. While automated detection of features on OSM has only recently become

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an important topic of research, ongoing studies have primarily focused on the accuracy or credibility of this endeavour [6].

While existing studies of digital communities have focused on the socialities they engender or labor they require, they tend to forget the bureaucratic apparatuses that have emerged to govern them, both implicitly and explicitly. Similarly, studies of humanitarianism have focused on the ethics they operationalize, or the technologies that are mobilized in turn, but often at the expense of engaging in the wider spectrum of social and economic life that they enable. [7–10] While this project draws upon these overlapping strains of research, it seeks to push the debate in an ethnographic direction, scaffolded by theories of bureaucratic technology, political economy, and humanitarianism.

This research draws from participation in over 40 online events over 1.5 years, including mapathons, conferences and online lectures with OSM mappers, as well as semi-structured interviews conducted with 27 key-informants, alongside watching more conference videos, and reading blogs, mailing list emails, Twitter exchanges, and other internet archives. While empirically influenced by studies of hacking and open source software, this work ultimately focuses on the mechanisms and means through which this “free and open map” is created, and ultimately the ways of seeing and doing that it enables.

The “supply chains” heuristic emerged as a means to understand and illustrate this process. Similar to how supply chains “link ostensibly independent entrepreneurs, making it possible for commodity processes to span the globe”, the OSM project relies upon a series of interconnected processes that enable the creation of the world’s crowdsourced map [11]. Similar to how the satellite, computer, and software industries converged to create the conditions that allowed for OSM’s creation, so do people – and their associated institutions create map data through an almost miraculous collision of circumstances, assured precedent, and training. HOT, which is the initial entry point into open source mapping, made its name by optimizing the mapping value chain: that is, by making it easier to contribute to OSM. But it also extended outwards: contributing to OSM was enabled not only by the wider socio-economic forces that coalesced to produce the project in the first place, but also by a series of digital value chains – both past and present.

By delineating this supply-chains approach, this study hopes to scaffold a mental model of humanitarian mapping and the OSM more broadly, to be employed in future studies – both quantitative and qualitative. Practically, it hopes to provide a heuristic and application of ethnographic tools, and present questions and queries directly to the community more broadly.

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